

RAISING CHILDREN THROUGH OUTDOOR GAMES

Tashpulatov Farkhad Alisherovich

Head of the department of "Physical culture and sports activity" of the
Tashkent Financial Institute, associate professor
tashpulatov.fa@gmail.com

Abstract:

This article describes raising children using outdoor games. Outdoor games are usually considered as a means of exercising children in walking, running, jumping and other types of movements. The need for movement, the physical activity of a child, physiologically based, has a positive effect on his physical and mental development, improvement of all functional systems of the body.

Keywords:

Outdoor games, movements, physical activity, gaming activity, physical qualities, strength, dexterity, accuracy, exercises.

Анотация:

В данной статье описывается воспитание детей с помощью подвижных игр. Подвижные игры принято рассматривать как средство упражнения детей в ходьбе, беге, прыжках и других видах движений. Потребность в движениях, двигательная активность ребенка, физиологически обоснованная, положительно влияет на его физическое и психическое развитие, совершенствование всех функциональных систем организма.

Ключевые слова:

Подвижные игры, движения, двигательная активность, игровая деятельность, физические качества, сила, ловкость, меткость, упражнения.

Play is of great importance in a child's life. "What a child is like at play, so in many ways he will be at work when he grows up," said A. S. Makarenko. The game provides the initial education of many qualities necessary for a future citizen. Children willingly and with interest do things that outside the game may seem uninteresting and difficult to them. Therefore, during the game process, it is easier for the teacher to influence the child and develop his desire to achieve his goal.

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physical activity of a child, physiologically based, has a positive effect on his physical and mental development, improvement of all functional systems of the body.

Children's mastery of the skills of basic movements, mastering the correct ways to perform them enriches the motor experience necessary in play activities, various life situations, work and everyday life. For this purpose, special classes are conducted with children to develop movements, teach them to walk, run, and jump correctly.

By imitating adults or favorite characters in games, children show independence and navigate their surroundings. Games contribute to the development of attention, thinking, memory, imagination, and a sense of camaraderie. They captivate children and serve as an excellent means of strengthening health and developing physical qualities. In games, children develop strength, dexterity, accuracy, strengthen their will, learn to quickly navigate in any environment, develop determination, organization and discipline.

In play, children clearly reveal their personal qualities and properties. By studying the character of children and their behavior during play, the teacher can prevent the possibility of insufficient organization, excessive agitation, disputes, non-compliance with the rules of the game, and help develop courage in children; perseverance, sense of camaraderie, collectivism. The teacher helps the child develop his creative activity and demonstrate his personal initiative.

Introducing a variety of options into a game situation ensures that children consolidate their knowledge of spatial categories, helps them see familiar content differently, understand it better, and also acquire knowledge about direction, location, and the relationship between objects. Setting more complex tasks causes children to strive to find the right solution, develops ingenuity, endurance, and attention. New variants of the game associated with determining the direction of movement require orientation in new conditions.

The success of the game largely depends on the teacher's ability to interest children, explain its rules in an interesting and intelligible way, skillfully manage the game process, and be impartial and attentive in assessing children's game actions.

It is important to instill in children a serious attitude towards the game and discipline, the habit of playing honestly, strictly following the rules, and acting amicably and unitedly in the interests of the team.

One of the most important moments in managing the game is the dosage of the load. It depends on the exercises preceding the games and on the activity of the players. Often children, carried away by the game and wanting to show their dexterity, forget about fatigue. Lack of control on the part of the teacher can lead to overwork in children, which negatively affects their health.

An essential feature of outdoor games is the presence of competition and cooperation in them. Elements of competition occupy a leading place in the main game actions; cooperation, as a rule, is determined by specific circumstances and tasks. By selecting exercises and entertainment in a certain combination or sequence, the teacher can influence the development of necessary social relationships in children and enrich their feelings and skills.

Elements of sports in games help increase the capabilities of a child's body. Thanks to sports exercises, children master the technique of performing movements, individual combinations of movements in sports games, and orientation in space and time.

When working with preschoolers, you should use sports exercises and entertainment in which the maximum available physical activity would alternate with minimal movements - walking, running, jumping, throwing, catching, throwing a ball, climbing, etc.

Games and entertainment should be carried out outdoors. Therefore, when selecting them, weather conditions should be taken into account.

When leading games and entertainment, the teacher widely uses a variety of methods of teaching and raising children - explanation, showing, indicating, evaluating actions, encouraging, and example of another child. At the same time, children should always be supported emotionally.

Of great importance is the use of games and entertainment in the daily routine in combination with the inclusion of exercises that differ in motor content, level, assimilation and technical complexity. A variety of movements helps improve the overall physical fitness of children. The use of entertainment with different levels of complexity facilitates the organization and pedagogical control of their progress.

When choosing sports games, you need to strive to use them to find the most rational methods of teaching children basic movements, to enrich the content of walks at different times of the year, to strengthen in children the habits of mutual assistance and support, to subordinate personal desires to the interests of the team, the ability to see, evaluate beautiful in dexterous, precise, fast movements, in coordination of actions.

The number of repetitions of games and entertainment, the duration of mastery of the movement largely depends on the complexity, significance and conditions of implementation.

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